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**CHALLENGING ASPECTS OF THE RENAL
PHYTOPHARMACOLOGY. REVIEW OF THE EVIDENCE IN THE
LITERATURE AND THE RESULTS OF THE OWN EXPERIMENTAL
STUDIES OF THE NEPHROTROPIC PLANT – GOUTWEED
(*AEGOPODIUM PODAGRARIA L.*)**

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**ПРОБЛЕМНІ ПИТАННЯ ФІТОФАРМАКОЛОГІЇ НИРОК.
ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ ТА РЕЗУЛЬТАТИ ВЛАСНИХ
ЕКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНИХ ДОСЛІДЖЕНЬ НЕФРОТРОПНОЇ
РОСЛИНИ ЯГЛИЦІ ЗВИЧАЙНОЇ (*AEGOPODIUM PODAGRARIA L.*)**

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**ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИТОФАРМАКОЛОГИИ ПОЧЕК.
ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ СОБСТВЕННЫХ
ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ НЕФРОТРОПНОГО
РАСТЕНИЯ СНЫТИ ОБЫКНОВЕННОЙ (*AEGOPODIUM
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Summary/Резюме

Introduction. The problem of the verification of the nephrotropic activity and concomitant effects of the agents of herbal origin remains relevant despite a large body of evidence that has been obtained.

The aim of this review is to elucidate the challenging issues in the renal phytopharmacology (excluding nephroprotectors of plant origin or nephrotoxins). *Materials and methods.* Bibliometric, analytical, analysis of the own experimental results. *Research results.* The following aspects were analysed: abundance of the medicinal plants possessing diuretic activity, medicinal plants activity in view of synergism, permissive action and hormesis phenomena, the specifics of the research in the field of renal phytopharmacology, the possible molecular mechanisms of action of diuretics of herbal origin, the antidiuretic action of herbal agents, their influence on potassium exchange, as well as possibility of modulation of the effects of hydrochlorothiazide by these agents. Complexity of neprotropic effects of herbal preparations and their mechanisms were considered on the example of goutweed (*Aegopodium podagraria* L.) pharmacological preparations, previously studied by the authors.

Key words: medicinal plants, biologically active substances of herbal origin, kidneys, mechanisms of action.

Вступ. Проблема верифікації нефротропної активності та супутніх ефектів засобів рослинного походження залишається актуальною, незважаючи на великий обсяг наявних даних. *Метою даної роботи* є висвітлення проблемних питань ниркової фітофармакології (за винятком рослинних нефропротекторів та нефротоксинів). *Матеріали і методи.* Бібліометричний, аналітичний, аналіз результатів власних експериментів. *Результати дослідження.* Проаналізовано наступні аспекти: численність видів лікарських рослин, що виявляють діуретичну дію, активність препаратів лікарських рослин з огляду на явища синергізму та гормезису, специфіку досліджень у галузі ниркової фітофармакології, можливі молекулярні механізми дії діуретиків рослинного походження, антидіуретичні властивості рослинних препаратів, їх вплив на калієвий обмін, а також можливість модуляції ефектів гідрохлортіазиду цими препаратами. Багатогранність нефротропних ефектів препаратів рослинного походження та їх механізмів розглянуто на прикладі раніше досліджених авторами фармакологічних препаратів яглиці звичайної (*Aegopodium podagraria* L.).

Ключові слова: лікарські рослини, біологічно активні речовини рослинного походження, нирки, механізми дії.

Вступление. Проблема верификации нефротропной активности и сопутствующих эффектов средств растительного происхождения остается актуальной, невзирая на большой объем имеющихся данных. *Целью данной работы* является освещение проблемных вопросов почечной фитотерапии (кроме растительных нефропротекторов и нефротоксинов). *Материалы и методы.* Библиометрический, аналитический анализ результатов собственных экспериментов. *Результаты исследования.* Проанализированы следующие аспекты: многочисленность видов лекарственных растений, обладающих диуретической активностью, активность лекарственных растений с учетом явлений синергизма и гормезиса, специфика исследований в области почечной фитотерапии, возможные молекулярные механизмы действия диуретиков растительного происхождения, антидиуретическое действие растительных препаратов, а также возможность модуляции эффектов гидрохлоротиазида этими препаратами. Многогранность нефротропных эффектов препаратов растительного происхождения и их механизмов рассмотрены на примере ранее исследованных авторами фармакологических препаратов сныти обыкновенной (*Aegopodium podagraria* L.).

Ключевые слова: лекарственные растения, биологически активные вещества растительного происхождения, почки, механизмы действия.

Introduction

The problem of the verification of the nephrotropic activity and concomitant effects of the agents of herbal origin remains relevant despite a large body of evidence that has been obtained.

The aim of this review is to elucidate the challenging issues in the renal phytopharmacology (without characterising the nephroprotectors of plant origin or nephrotoxins, which can be the themes of other voluminous reviews).

1. Abundance of the medicinal plants possessing diuretic activity

Medicinal plants have represented a source of traditional medicines since time immemorial, and targeting the renal function turned out to be one of the most common effects inherent in these agents. Thus, in the Canon of Medicine by Abu-Ali-Ibn-Sina (Avicenna), written almost 1000 years ago, 124 plants with a diuretic effect are mentioned. De Materia Medica by Dioscorides, which has remained the main source of information on herbal medicines for many centuries, lists more than 200 medicinal plants used for diseases of the urinary system (citation by source [1]).

Even among the plants cited in the Bible, the expertise for searching the diuretic plants has been conducted, and the authors make a really deep-rooting conclusion, namely “the loss of the empirical wisdom developed from human interactions with the environment over millennia is the loss of a fundamental part of our cultural heritage” [2].

In general, the number of medicinal plants considered to possess diuretic properties is very high compared with the species exerting other types of pharmacological activity [3]. As noted by the great cardiologist B.E. Votchal: “practically all herbs exert a diuretic effect” [4]. In this regard, it is advisable to address the hypothesis formulated by Dearing M.D. et al. (2001): the ability to increase diuresis may be a general property of herbal secondary metabolites. This property could have been sup-

ported through natural selection, since it contributed to a reduction of plants consumption by herbivores, in which increased losses of Na⁺ and water disturbed the water-electrolyte balance. Maintaining the latter was associated with certain difficulties, since almost always there was a shortage of either Na⁺ (temperate zones) or water (in desert areas) [5]. Of course, the latter is true with regard to the wild animals, but not domesticated ones that have changed their diet fundamentally, as well as humans who have recently been living on a hypersodium diet [6]. Thus, the loss of a limited resource – Na⁺ or water – becomes a factor that reduces the consumption of certain plants by animals. According to the authors of this hypothesis, these evolutionary-ecological patterns may be one of the reasons for the abundance of plants with diuretic properties [5]. These aspects were also described in details our previous work [7].

Possibly, for the reason explained above, the ethnopharmacological search of diuretic medicinal plants appeared to be quite efficient in different regions of the world, and a large body of evidence has been obtained [8–12]. Recently, similar search has been continued and especially comprehensive data are coming from Brazilian scientists as elucidated in the robust reviews [13–15]. At the same time, the principally new methodological approaches have arisen and are being successfully used for the verification of activity of the agents from traditional medicine, for instance, metabolomics analysis has been applied for the evaluation of diuretic activity of *Plantago asiatica* L. (*Plantaginaceae*) [16] as well as for the elucidation of the influence of the complex herbal drug from the traditional Chinese medicine “Ermiao wan” influence on kidney function including uric acid excretion [17]. The possibilities of direct measurement of hormones and regulatory agents directly related to kidney function and water-electrolyte homeostasis have significantly expanded the possibilities of verification of the nephrotropic agents mechanisms of action. For in-

stance, in the study [16], untargeted metabolomic analysis was supplemented by the estimation of serum aquaporin 2 and aldosterone concentrations.

Pharmacokinetics aspects can be profoundly described at the modern stage, for example the metabolic pathways of biologically active substances present in *Filipendula ulmaria* (L.) Maxim. (*Rosaceae*) and *Orthosiphon aristatus* (Blume) Miq. (*Lamiaceae*), which are widely used in urinary infections, have been investigated, and it was confirmed that the compounds with anti-inflammatory and diuretic activity are formed by the microbiota [18]

And finally, the evaluation of the possible toxicity has reached a new level through the advance in the scientific methods. For instance, proteome changes in human bladder T24 cells induced by hydroquinone were documented in the study [19] thus confirming the possibility of negative effects even in bearberry *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* (L.) Spreng. (*Ericaceae*) which has been a well-known traditional uroantiseptic for centuries.

Due to the presence of the numerous dietary supplements which can not undergo strict control of composition and safety, the problem of nephrotoxicity of herbal agents remains urgent. Since this aspect is not described in details in the present work, two robust reviews that have appeared recently [20, 21] can be addressed in this context.

2. Medicinal plants activity in view of synergism, permissive action and hormesis phenomena

Given that the medicinal plants possess a complex composition and polytropic effect, it is highly important that concomitant effects significant in the pathogenesis of “diseases of civilization” are possible, such as anti-diabetic and anti-hypertensive activity [22], the influence on the different links of cardiovascular diseases pathogenesis [14, 23, 24] or the concomitant influence on uric acid exchange as was shown in our previous work [7] as well as in the

recent reviews of the other authors [25–28].

Modern data allow us to rethink the approaches to the herbal biologically active substances – from the commonly used albeit ungrounded statements characterising their action as “mild” and “natural” to the consideration of these molecules being capable of targeted influence on well-known pathogenetically important sites of action. Two shining examples of such molecules which fundamentally changed the possibilities of improving the prognosis in type 2 diabetes are metformin based on the structure of the alkaloid galegine and dapagliflozin as an analogue of phlorizin. Important renal effects are also inherent in these molecules.

The reason for the high biological activity of the herbal biologically active substances is a fundamental difference in the metabolism of plant cells, namely the synthesis of a large number of substances which are not components of the basic biochemical processes (secondary metabolites) but provide protective effects on the plant cell and a plant organism as a whole. The need in such metabolites arises in connection with lack of ability to move, unique immune mechanisms (not inherent in animals) of plants. This directly determines certain types of pharmacological activity of these compounds, namely, the antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, antioxidative, and these effects are also important in case of renal pathology.

At the same time, the realization of the effects of the herbal biologically active substances may seem problematic since they are present in the herbal raw material in respectively low doses and thus being taken at low doses. In this context, it has been proposed to apply the phenomenon of hormesis for the substantiation of the efficacy of herbal metabolites. Thus, the adaptive reactions may arise against the background of low doses of substances that are toxic at high doses, and the involvement of signaling kinases, transcription factors and histone deacetylases, leads to the formation of proteins that enhance

the survival of cells under stress conditions: chaperones, anti-apoptotic substances, antioxidant enzymes. In addition, since all combined herbal preparations are, by definition, mixtures, their activity despite the presence of individual components at low doses is explained by the phenomenon of synergism (from numerous extracts it has not been possible to isolate components or fractions with higher activity than the original extract) [29–33]. According to P. Houghton (2009) [34] there are the following types of interactions of herbal biologically active substances (leading to the spectrum of activities, i.e. the polyvalence): the presence of several compounds with different biological effects; the presence of substances with a pleiotropic mechanism of action of pathogenetic or symptomatic type in regard with certain disease pathogenesis; the influence of certain compounds, which are not active by their own, on the pharmacokinetics of active components [34].

If the statistically significant effect is not registered after the action of a single agent, but is seen against the background of combination of two agents, the concept of a permissive action can be successfully applied for the characteristic of agents of herbal origin interaction.

The foregoing patterns are especially important in case of nephroprotection, antihypertensive or antidiabetic activity. Because of the multifactorial pathogenesis of the “diseases of civilization,” targeting the single mechanism is not always highly effective, and the concepts of multi-agent medicines and network pharmacology have been developed. If several compounds show a moderate activity towards the proteins of the same signaling pathway, this may be sufficient to trigger a certain reaction (and such properties are inherent in metformin exerting multidirectional activity partially due to low-affinity interactions with proteins) [30, 35–37].

3. The specifics of the research in the field of renal phytopharmacology

As mentioned above, the number of medicinal plants considered to possess diuretic activity is very high; still, the problem of its verification remains relevant. The comprehensive list of the species of medicinal plants (as at 2014) possessing the verified diuretic effect has been given by us in the source [7]. The data about the active components and the principal mechanism of action (GFR increase or reabsorption inhibition) were also summarized in that source.

After data analysis, certain methodological problems became evident. The fundamental problem among them is the necessity of considering the regimen of the kidney functioning. The majority of studies were carried out under conditions of induced diuresis – water or saline loading, whereas data obtained under conditions of spontaneous diuresis are much less common. The quality of water used for loading should also be described (as well as parameters of drinking water and mineral composition of the diet consumed by the animals during the chronic studies of the excretory renal function), while the use of distilled water for this purpose should be considered as inappropriate. In the experimental research, the species of laboratory animals used in the study is also an important factor [7], while clinical studies in the field of phytopharmacology are understandably scarce. Nevertheless, there are modern articles verifying the experience of traditional medicines even in severe pathological states, albeit at the level of a clinical observation, for instance, in the work [38], the clinical experience of successful treatment of refractory edema with traditional herbal agent is described.

Chronorhythm influence is also a fundamental issue, and the data concerning the time of certain experiments conducting are often omitted. There are certain examples of chronopharmacological factors in the action of the nephrotropic plants [7, 39].

Besides, there is a problem of the relevant data analysis and interpretation. Unfortunately, the works can be found where instead of sodium or potassium excretion, the concentration of cations in the urine is given and erroneously characterized as “excretion,” thus not allowing to characterize the electrolyte excretions changes clearly and even sometimes misleading. These aspects were previously described in the source [7].

Obviously, the influence of doses and routes of administration (for individual substances) on the results obtained in renal phytopharmacology studies is crucial. For the crude extracts, the complex composition described above is a certain benefit, nevertheless it can be a reason of discrepancy in results if they were obtained for preparations from different types of herbal raw materials or with the help of various extractants (this information is not always available, especially if analyzing older data or in cases when only the abstract of the work is available). And clearly, there is a need in taking this data into consideration.

Thus, the object of our research – goutweed *Aegopodium podagraria* L. (*Apiaceae*) – is characterized by the diverse nephrotropic activity. The detailed analysis of the effects of goutweed preparations obtained from the different raw materials of *Aegopodium podagraria* L. has been conducted and it was shown that the extract of the rhizomes (100 mg/kg and 1 g/kg), inhibiting tubular reabsorption, tended to increase diuresis in a dose-dependent manner, while the leaves extract did not change the ratio “excreted/ administered fluid” in intact mice under conditions of water loading. The diuretic effect of the flowers extract at lower doses (100 and 250 mg/kg) was realized mainly due to increased glomerular filtration rate (GFR). The tinctures from all types of the studied raw materials reduced creatinine excretion, a dose-dependent diuretic effect was registered only in mice receiving goutweed flowers tincture. The protein-polysaccharide complex of goutweed (20 and 200 mg/kg)

and its component flavonoid trifolin (50 mg/kg) in the intact organism did not change the functional state of the kidneys, and the essential oil of the flowers (1 mg/kg) increased diuresis due to inhibition of reabsorption [40].

Goutweed aerial part tincture at doses of 1 and 5 ml/kg exerted a dose-dependent diuretic (due to the inhibition of tubular reabsorption) and uricosuric effect under the conditions of spontaneous diuresis in rats. The effect of goutweed pharmacological preparations, especially the tincture, on the excretory renal function was partly attributed to the increase in renal blood flow [39].

The well-known interconnectedness between the changes in the GFR and reabsorption is clearly seen in the realization of the renal effects of the herbal drugs. Some of them demonstrate the patterns which could be considered as unexpected ones. Thus, the extract of goutweed aerial part extract (the extractant is water) after course administration significantly increased GFR (by 79%, $p < 0.05$). During the first days of using the extract, Na^+ reabsorption was significantly reduced (by 2.3%, $p < 0.02$) and its excretion correspondingly increased. At the same time, there was an increment in reabsorption of water, enabling diuresis unchangeability. Therefore, a direct inhibitory effect of the biologically active substances of the extract on Na^+ reabsorption is possible, resulting in the activation of the mechanisms of ADH-dependent water transport, as a protective reaction counteracting dehydration [39].

The similar patterns are elucidated in the literature. The extract of begonia *Begonia erythrophylla* hort. J. Neumann (*Begoniaceae*) increased GFR and reduced Na^+ reabsorption, thus excretion of the latter was elevated, but due to the increase in water reabsorption, diuresis was not significantly changed [41]. The extract of purslane *Portulaca oleracea* L. (*Portulacaceae*) at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg dose-dependently increased natriuresis and kaliuresis, while diuresis was elevated only

against the background of higher dose [42]. Such herbal preparations as water-ethanol extract of *Hieracium pilopsella* L. (*Asteraceae*) and water extract of *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* (L.) Spreng. (*Ericaceae*) possess a verified diuretic activity, but do not increase Na^+ excretion [43]. The crude water extract of *Eugenia uniflora* L. (*Myrtaceae*) elevates diuresis, but reduces Na^+ excretion, the authors associate the mechanism of diuretic action with an increase in renal blood flow [44], though it could be considered disputable.

The drugs containing individual flavonoid quercetin in the different medicinal forms “Corvitin” and “Lipoflavon” (8 mg/kg as quercetin intraperitoneally) significantly increased GFR in the experiment, however, due to the mechanism of glomerular-tubular balance, reabsorption was enhanced and diuresis was changed insignificantly [45].

The absence of concurrency between the influence on saluresis and hydrouresis is inherent in the “Maxar” – preparation of wood of amur maackia *Maackia amurensis* Rupr. et Maxim. (*Fabaceae*). This herbal agent is characterized by a diuretic effect with a gradual increment in effect and its subsequent slow decrease (dose of 100 mg/kg under the conditions of spontaneous diuresis in rats). At the same time, excretion of creatinine and Na^+ remained unchanged, indicating a selective inhibition of tubular water reabsorption through mechanisms relatively independent of natriuresis. This action can be localized in the thin descending loop of Henle and targeted at the inhibition of aquaporins, primarily AQP1. This mechanism is indirectly confirmed by an increase in diuresis with a lesser effect on kaliuresis and unchanged creatinine excretion [46].

The specifics patterns of the influence on the excretory renal function were also registered for polyphenolic complexes of callus cell cultures of *Eritrichium sericeum* Lehm. and *Lithospermum erythrorhizon* Sieb. et Zucc. (*Boraginaceae*). The absence of concurrency between the influ-

ence on saluresis and hydrouresis may indicate that the agents do not target the reabsorption of Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- ions in the ascending loop of Henle. The diuretic effect of these drugs is associated mainly with an increase in GFR and additional inhibition of tubular water reabsorption, mainly in the descending loop of Henle, permeable to water, diffusing without concomitant reabsorption of electrolytes [46].

Such phenomenon as natriuretic effect of herbal preparations without changes in hydrouresis is also possible. Water extract of *Centaureum erythraea* Rafn. (*Gentianaceae*) at a dose of 10 ml/kg (of a 16% solution) did not change diuresis, still increased Na^+ excretion in rats [47]. The similar results on mice (under the conditions of saline loading) were obtained in the study [48] for ether and chloroform extracts of dandelion *Taraxacum officinale* L. (*Asteraceae*) roots. The crude extract and the methanolic extract from this herbal raw material did not possess such properties and also did not change hydrouresis [48]. Ethanol extract of the leaves of ash tree *Fraxinus excelsior* L. (*Oleaceae*) at a dose of 1400 mg/kg increased natriuresis without affecting the volume of urine. Water extract at a dose of 165 mg/kg shows similar effects, which were less significant [49].

Ethanol and water extracts of *Euphorbia hirta* L. (*Euphorbiaceae*) leaves at doses of 50 and 100 mg/kg have been shown to exert diuretic properties, however, these preparations differ in the profile of their saluretic action: against the background of water extract, excretion of Na^+ , K^+ and HCO_3^- increased (similarity to acetazolamide), while ethanol extract had a similar effect only on HCO_3^- , renal excretion of K^+ was reduced, excretion of Na^+ – did not change [50].

In the study [51] the renal effects of the water extract of maize *Zea mays* L. (500 mg/kg) were profoundly studied. It has been shown that the extract which increased hydrouresis and kaliuresis, however, reduced creatinine clearance and the filtered load of Na^+ , its reabsorption was

decreased in the proximal tubules and intensified – in the distal ones, as a result there were no changes in the excretion of Na^+ .

The aforementioned data illustrate the multidimensionality of the renal effects of medicinal plants, requiring profound analysis and comprehensive approach.

4. The possible molecular mechanisms of action of diuretics of herbal origin

The diuretic agents of herbal origin can target the fundamental mechanisms, such example could be given as inhibition of Na^+ , K^+ -ATPase by flavonoids (for which even the structure-activity relationship was established) [52]. Anthraquinone derivatives isolated from rhubarb *Rheum* L. inhibit Na^+ , K^+ -ATPase in rabbit renal medulla and exert diuretic action [53].

Flavonoids also exert a specific influence on Na^+ - K^+ - 2Cl^- -cotransporter [54], while isoflavonoids can inhibit furosemid-dependent Na^+ - K^+ - 2Cl^- -cotransporters [55, 56]. Isoflavonoids which are regarded as phytoestrogens are actively studied due to their presence in the dietary sources and possible involvement into the beneficial effects of certain dietary regimens, such as vegetarian diet. In this context, saluretic properties of genistein were analyzed and it has been shown that they are caused by inhibition of Na^+ - K^+ - 2Cl^- -cotransporter in the thick ascending limb of the loop of Henle, and genistein effect on the isolated perfused kidney is comparable with that of furosemide [56]. The inhibitory influence of genistein on tyrosine kinases was studied, and it was shown that it is a competitor at the ATP-binding site, this effect could be not indifferent to the processes of ion exchange and vascular tone regulation [57]. Despite the possibility of unfavourable effects proceeding from targeting tyrosine kinases involved into multidirectional cell signaling (in this regard, lack of prospects in genistein use as a saluretic in the form of an individual compound are considered [56]), the general profile of genistein activ-

ity appeared to be beneficial for the kidney and its nephroprotective properties are described in details [58].

Activity of phlorizin as dapagliflozin predecessor was mentioned above. Phlorizin is a dual SGLT1/SGLT2 inhibitor, and for some other flavonoids, the inhibitory activity against SGLTs has been also shown [59].

In the context of the current section, it is impossible not to mention the diuretic properties of cardiac glycosides. Since olden times, these properties were considered as a classic example of indirect pharmacological effects, being caused by normalization of hemodynamics and dilation of renal vessels [4]. But, nevertheless, the direct inhibition of Na^+ tubular transport by cardiac glycosides was experimentally confirmed. Increased diuresis was registered in rats against the background of cardiac glycosides, despite this species is characterized by low sensitivity to their cardiac effects; and in the experiments conducted in the distant past on dogs, these compounds suppressed the reabsorption of Na^+ and water in the kidneys at doses that do not cause significant changes in hemodynamics or after direct administration into blood flow of the kidney. Potassium, which decreases the cardiac effects of glycosides, changes the renal effects of strophanthin in the similar direction [12, 60, 61]. The mechanism of the diuretic action of eryzimine G is associated with a decrease in the activity of the apical 70-pS K^+ channel in the thick ascending limb of the loop of Henle [62]. In addition, the steroid structure of cardiac glycosides may contribute to antagonism with aldosterone [60, 63]. Besides, ergone, a metabolite present in mushrooms, also exhibits antagonism with aldosterone without a direct effect on Na^+ / K^+ ion channels [64].

A dopaminergic mechanism of the influence of herbal agents on saluresis and hydrouresis is also possible. Renal dopamine receptors are known to mediate an increase in diuresis and natriuresis. The possibility of increasing the intrarenal concen-

tration of dopamine *in situ* is largely determined by the availability of its precursor, L-DOPA. It was shown that L-DOPA is present in significant amounts in beans *Vicia faba* Pers. (*Fabaceae*) and is effectively absorbed from them. After the intake of 40 g of sprouts of this plant by volunteers (the content of L-DOPA is 120–130 mg), there was an increase in the level of L-DOPA in plasma as well as in the excretion of Na⁺ and dopamine, with an increment in the dopamine/creatinine and Na⁺/creatinine ratios [65].

The mechanism of the diuretic action of the complex herbal drug used to treat edema in the traditional oriental medicine “Sai-rei-to”, is associated with the NO-dependent mechanisms (NO was shown to exert hydrouretic effect). In anesthetized rats, the herbal drug caused a dose-dependent increment in diuresis and urea excretion as well as NO₂ + NO₃ urinary level, while blood pressure and Na⁺ excretion remained unchanged [66].

The data concerning the mechanisms of the renal effects of herbal secondary metabolites would undoubtedly be supplemented and deepened in future.

5. The antidiuretic action of herbal agents

The possibilities of the decline in the excretory renal function under the influence of xenobiotics also exist and are often realized by the agents of herbal origin. As reported in the source [7], there are numerous examples of antidiuretic action of medicinal plants and their biologically active compounds. Nevertheless, this aspect is insufficiently elucidated in the modern literature, thus, it is expedient to review the issue in detail.

For certain preparations, the antidiuretic effect can be considered as expected one, as for the agents increasing corticosteroid-mediated reactions and thus inducing fluid retention. For instance, it was shown that preparations of *Bupleurum falcatum* L. (*Apiaceae*) rhizomes and licorice *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. (*Fabaceae*) roots at

doses of 1 g/kg significantly increased the level of corticosterone in the blood (at the same time, this effect was considered as a mechanism of their efficacy in glomerulonephritis [67]). Water-ethanol extract of *Biophytum petersianum* Klotzsch. (*Oxalidaceae*) dose-dependently stimulated the secretion of corticosterone and aldosterone [68].

The classic example of corticosteroid-mediated side effects of herbal drugs is licorice *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. (*Fabaceae*). More than half a century ago, it was found that 20% of patients receiving licorice root preparations as an antiulcer agent (and even those who used large quantities of confectionery containing licorice) develop edema. After its prolonged use at high doses, hypokalemia, hypernatremia, hypertension and other cardiovascular disorders are possible, and because of this the interest in the anti-ulcer effect of licorice has weakened. Side effects of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L., as well as of *G. uralensis* Fisch. are dose-dependent, can develop even in normotensive individuals and become especially significant when licorice is combined with cardiac glycosides and diuretics. Even the development of life-threatening complications, such as hypokalemia and rhabdomyolysis, is possible [7, 61, 69].

In addition to local mineralocorticoid effects, glycyrrhizic and glycyrrhetic acids and their derivatives reduce the metabolism of corticosteroids in the liver, a long time ago these compounds were even recommended for the elimination of the withdrawal syndrome after corticosteroids discontinuation. Since olden times (beginning from the recommendations of Avicenna), licorice was used in the diseases of the urinary system, and it is possible that corticosteroid-mediated effects allowed to counteract inflammatory and autoimmune pathological processes in that case [61, 69].

The pseudohyperaldosteronism against the background of licorice was associated with glycyrrhizin metabolites, mainly 3-β-D-(monoglucuronyl)-18-β-gly-

cyrrhetic acid [70]. This effect (which develops in long-term use) is realized through a highly specific mechanism – inhibition of 11- β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 2 with the further increase in the concentration of cortisol in cells sensitive to mineralocorticoids. Under such conditions, cortisol, along with aldosterone, activates type I mineralocorticoid receptors causing the retention of Na⁺ and water. Increment in expression of aquaporins was also documented in this context, namely in rats after course administration of glycyrrhizin (200 mg/kg per day intragastrically) the increase in the expression of AQP 2 and AQP 3 in the medulla of the kidneys was registered. It was not accompanied with the changes in creatinine clearance and was eliminated by spironolactone [70]. Under normal conditions, such changes could be considered as unfavourable, still they also could contribute to polyuria elimination. Thus, glycyrrhizin has been shown to restore the synthesis of AQP 2 in gentamicin nephropathy [71]. In general, organoprotective (including nephroprotective) properties of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. preparations is under active research now on the models of kidney injury with different pathogenesis [72].

It should be noted that in the earliest sources licorice was included into the lists of the medicinal plants with diuretic activity (albeit a moderate one). As seems more probable, this activity is inherent in the aerial part of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. containing flavonoids with potential diuretic effect, namely quercetin, kaempferol, isorhamnetin, etc. [7, 61, 73].

Glycyrrhetic acid can exert a direct mineralocorticoid effect. *In vitro*, it has been shown that, unlike glycyrrhizic acid, it binds to mineralocorticoid and, to a lesser extent, to glucocorticoid receptors in the kidneys. Due to the low affinity, such an effect *in vivo* is possible only at high doses. Both acids do not bind to cortisol-binding globulin [69, 74].

The aspects of licorice-induced pseudohyperaldosteronism were addressed

on the most modern methodological level in the study [75] with human volunteers participation. Identification of pseudoaldosterogenic compounds was performed for *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch. after taking the complex herbal drug from the traditional Chinese medicine containing the mentioned herbal raw material (notably, this drug has the evidence of efficacy in patients with COVID-19, and the cited study aimed at substantiation of conditions for its safe use). It has been shown that glycyrrhizin and licorice saponin are metabolically activated to the pseudoaldosterogenic compounds glycyrrhetic acid and 24-hydroxyglycyrrhetic acid (this metabolite was firstly described in this study), which, due to good membrane permeability, could access (via passive tubular reabsorption) and inhibit renal 11- β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 2 [75].

At the same time, the inhibitors of 11- β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase of plant origin are not limited to licorice metabolites. The IC₅₀ values of naringenin with regard to this enzyme are close to those of glycyrrhizic acid. Moreover, grapefruit flavonoids are reported to dose-dependently inhibit both forms of this enzyme (NAD⁺ and NADPH-dependent) [76]. Given that the inhibition of type 1 isoform could possibly contribute to the decrease in glucocorticoid concentrations, the different resulting effect on the kidney function and the metabolic processes may be expected. Nevertheless, the consequences of type 2 isoform suppression were verified *in vivo* by a decrease in the urine cortisone/cortisol ratio in healthy volunteers taking grapefruit juice. Thus, mineralocorticoid-like effects are possible even with the intake of significant amounts of flavonoids with food [77].

Finally, besides interactions at the level of aldosterone quantity and signaling, mineralocorticoid effects enhancement can be caused by excessive potassium supplementation. In this case, the intensity of the activatory influence on aldosterone control would largely be determined (besides the dose influence, which is obvious) by the

rate of absorption and the subsequent shifts in kalemia. Interestingly, such phenomena can also be caused by herbal agents.

Obviously, a significant content of potassium in numerous crude herbal preparations is important for diuretic effect as well as for other types of pharmacological activity. However, just this feature of the mineral composition of plants – namely, the high potassium content (together with low sodium level) – became the evolutionary prerequisite for the formation of aldosterone control of the blood potassium level [60].

After intake of potassium at high doses, especially as a single dose per day, quite naturally, there is the decrease in urinary Na^+/K^+ ratio indicating enhancement of tubular aldosterone control. This can be caused by potassium intake not only in the form of salts within medicinal forms, but also with the crude herbal preparations. For example, a decoction of the roots of *Ficus racemosa* L. (*Moraceae*, 250, 500, 1000 mg/kg), which reduced natriuresis and diuresis in rats, decreased urine Na^+/K^+ ratio, indicating intensified mineralocorticoid control of distal tubules [78]. The aspects of potassium supplementation with the herbal agents are also discussed below.

Besides, diuresis decrease can be realized through the modulation of antidiuretic hormone (ADH) effects. ADH-like effect or potentiation of endogenous ADH were supposed as mechanisms of antidiuretic activity of water extract of *Scoparia dulcis* L. (*Scrophulariaceae*) herb shown under the conditions of extreme water loading in previously water-deprived rats [79], although the direct verification of this mechanism has not been done. Rajeswari J. et al. (2012) confirmed the antidiuretic properties of preparations of *Pandanus fascicularis* Lam. (*Pandanaceae*) aerial roots, which are used in traditional medicine to reduce urination, and indicate the possibility of using this plant to limit hydrouresis in diabetes insipidus [80].

Flavonoids are among the main components of the nephrotropic plants. Nevertheless, they also can exert an ambiguous influence on the kidney function, and dose-dependence can be a crucial factor at that. It is estimated that, in most cases, the diuretic effect of fractions of flavones is most significant at doses within the range between 10–12 mg/kg, and after a considerable increase in the dose, an antidiuretic effect may develop. For example, the fraction of flavones of *Centaurea depressa* M. B. (*Asteraceae*) at a dose of 500 mg/kg reduces diuresis in rats by 33 %, at doses of 200–100 mg/kg – does not change it, at a dose of 10 mg/kg – increases it by 27% [12].

Primary estimation of the renal effects of different groups of flavonoids showed that catechins and anthocyanins exert antidiuretic activity, while flavone derivatives possess a diuretic effect. However, this pattern is not always confirmed. For example, information about the renal effects of rutin is contradictory; in experiments *in vivo*, both diuretic properties and inhibition of diuresis were observed. There are data both on the antidiuretic properties of catechins, and on the absence of their effect on the excretory renal function. Thus, the catechin fraction of *Hypericum scabrum* L. (*Clusiaceae*) at a dose of 25 mg/kg does not change diuresis in rats, at a dose of 10 mg/kg – it reduced it by 19%. Catechins of green tea *Thea sinensis* L. (*Theaceae*) at a high dose of 150 mg/kg 2 times a day inhibited diuresis in healthy volunteers by 21% [7, 12, 73, 81].

The inhibition of diuresis observed in several studies after the administration of preparations of bearberry *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* (L.) Spreng (*Ericaceae*) was associated with the influence of tannins (as well as of saponins), which decrease well-known diuretic activity of arbutin and flavonoids [12, 60].

Anthocyanins attract great attention nowadays due to their cytoprotective, favourable metabolic and antioxidative properties. The renal effects of these com-

pounds have been firstly verified in the study [12], and the fractions of anthocyanins of *Centaurea depressa* M. B. (*Asteraceae*) and *Tamarix hispida* Willd. (*Tamaricaceae*) decreased diuresis in rats, the most significant effect was seen at a dose 20 mg/kg. At the same time, anthocyanins are not considered to be the main active components of these plants, and the crude preparations obtained from them demonstrated diuretic properties *in vivo* [12], moreover, the activity of cornflower *Centaurea cyanus* L. (*Asteraceae*), widely used as diuretic, was associated specifically with anthocyanins, and their content was used in herbal raw material standardization [7].

As for simple phenolic compounds, the contribution of arbutin to the diuretic properties of medicinal plants is well known, and the saluretic activity of tremuloidin has been proven. Another salicylic acid glycoside, salicin exerted the effects typical for COX inhibitors, and at a dose of 10 mg/kg subcutaneously (course administration) it reduced diuresis, the excretion of Na⁺, K⁺, and creatinine under conditions of water diuresis in rats. In anesthetized animals, salicin at a dose of 25 mg/kg intravenously sharply inhibited filtration and reduced the fractional excretion of Na⁺ [82].

And additionally, there are examples of renal haemodynamics negative changes induced by herbal agents, the mechanism of these changes have not been elucidated in details. Dilation of the renal vessels is reported more often (for example, that caused by flavonoids), the opposite effect is also possible. Thus, the tincture of *Paeonia anomala* L. (*Paeoniaceae*) constricted the renal capillaries, and the effect of the infusion of *Astragalus dasyanthus* Pall. (*Fabaceae*) on the renal vessels depended on their functional state and on the dose, the extract of *Vandellia cordifolia* (Colsm) G. Don (*Scrophulariaceae*) reduced renal blood flow in rabbits [7, 61].

Some *in vivo* studies have established the antidiuretic properties of biologically active substances, commonly known as diuretics, namely essential oils. For exam-

ple, the essential oil obtained from the fruits of anise *Anisum vulgare* Gaertn. (*Apiaceae*), when added to drinking water, even at very low concentrations, reduced diuresis in rats. The mechanism of antidiuretic action was linked to an increase in the activity of Na⁺,K⁺-ATPase with a more intensive tubular reabsorption of Na⁺. By a similar mechanism, the oil enhanced the absorption of glucose in the small intestine [83]. The essential oil of *Anthemis nobilis* L. (*Asteraceae*) decreased diuresis, although water extract of this plant caused a diuretic effect [84]. Thus, individual biologically active substances and crude extracts from certain herbal raw material can influence the excretory renal function in the opposite way.

Among the another agents able to cause antidiuretic action, there are adaptogenic medicinal plants such as *Eleutherococcus senticosus* (Rupr. et Makino) Maxim. and *Panax ginseng* C.A Mey (*Araliaceae*) as well as its components panaxosides and polysaccharide fraction [85], paeoniflorin from *Paeonia anomala* L. (*Paeoniaceae*) [86], alkaloids rauwolscine [87], stachydrine [12], and allantoin (the data about the latter are controversial, and diuretic effect was also reported) [7, 12].

Analysis of the inhibitory effect of medicinal plants on the excretory renal function and further study of its mechanisms is one of the important tasks of the renal phytopharmacology.

6. Potassium exchange, the kidney and medicinal plants.

Hypokalemia prevention through the use of medicinal plants as a way to counteract the pathogenesis of the “diseases of civilization”

Human and human predecessors diet was previously characterized by a significant supply of potassium from plant sources and a relative deficit of sodium. Under these conditions, the mechanisms of Na⁺ sparing and hypersensitivity to salt have been formed (including the changes in renal vessels and interstitium, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system).

The fundamental changes in the dietary mineral composition of the modern humans with an excess of sodium salts and a lack of potassium salts are involved in the development of arterial hypertension as well as in the progression of pathological changes in the kidneys and other pathological processes important for the increase in morbidity within the modern populations. Correction of the mineral composition of the diet is an effective way of preventing “diseases of civilization” and increasing the effectiveness and safety of pharmacotherapy, since it proved possible to modulate in this way the effects of many drugs: antihypertensive, diuretic, antidiabetic, and even psychotropic drugs, as well as drugs that normalize cerebral blood circulation. At the same time, it is important to develop such methods that can be realized in practice, since the “restrictive approach” in regard with use of dietary salt is quite problematic, especially considering that this decrease of salt use should be long-term [6, 88, 89].

At the same time, positive effects can be achieved by increasing the intake of potassium salts from plant sources (both food plants and herbal preparations – dietary supplements or drugs), and this is a natural source of potassium compounds, for which a favourable pharmacokinetic profile can also be expected. Unfortunately, studies on the bioavailability of potassium salts from plant sources and comparative characteristics of such plants are extremely scarce. Thus, it was established that in consuming potatoes, the bioavailability of K⁺ ions approaches that of potassium gluconate [90]. In the study [91], favourable changes in the endothelium were registered after supplementation the diet with plant products rich in potassium salts.

On the other hand, herbal drugs or dietary supplements of herbal origin can be considered as the source of potassium salts. As summarized in our previous work [7], the role of potassium compounds in the realization of the diuretic activity of the preparations of *Carica papaya* L. (*Caricaceae*), *Smilax canariensis* Willd. (*Smilacace-*

ae), *Cocos nucifera* L. (*Arecaceae*), *Taraxacum officinale* L. (*Asteraceae*) has been confirmed. In herbal preparations that exhibit a diuretic effect, the K⁺/Na⁺ ratio is higher compared with those which do not possess such activity [92]. Unfortunately, in most studies, information on the mineral composition of herbal preparations is limited to data on the total content of macro- and microelements, often in the herbal raw materials, and there is a great need to determine the mineral composition of the final medicinal forms taken by a patient [93].

Above were considered the aspects of the absence of concurrency between the influence on saluresis and hydrouresis, and the similar difficulties arise with regard to K⁺ excretion. Unfortunately, often the experimental data are scarce making problematic the profound analysis of the mechanisms of the kidney handling of potassium delivered with the herbal agents. For instance, water-ethanol extract of *Portulaca pilosa* L. (*Portulacaceae*) increased the excretion of K⁺, without changing the excretion of Na⁺ and water in rats [94]. Water extract of *Capraria biflora* L. (*Scrophulariaceae*) leaves exerted kaliuretic effect in rats, still did not influence the ratio “excreted/ administered fluid” under the conditions of water diuresis [95], as well as water extract of maize *Zea mays* L. (*Poaceae*), which increased the excretion of K⁺ and Cl⁻, but not natriuresis and urine volume [96]. The results concerning renal effects of *Zea mays* L. preparations are quite diverse, as was mentioned above and also discussed in the source [7].

The object of our research mentioned above, goutweed (*Aegopodium podagraria* L.) aerial part extract, which contains a significant amount of potassium (that can reach 5,9 %), at doses of 100 mg/kg and 1 g/kg reduced the urine Na⁺/K⁺ ratio both in spontaneous diuresis and under the conditions of water loading. After the use of the extract at a dose of 1 g/kg, the intake of potassium and its renal excretion are comparable (410 mM/100 g and 624 mM/100 g, respectively), thus, the macroelement is

sufficiently excreted by the kidneys. An increment in kaliuresis was observed in all series of experiments [39, 40]. At the same time, the benefits of the extract use are partially linked to its ability to supplement potassium. Namely, under the conditions of gentamicin nephropathy, which, in contrast to other nephropathies, is accompanied with a decrease in the concentration of potassium and magnesium in the blood due to their tubular wasting [97], the extract showed a significant nephroprotective effect in rats, normalizing the excretory renal function, reducing proteinuria and hyperazotemia, as well as pathological changes in the kidneys histological structure. Notably, some of the studies confirmed protective effect of potassium preparations on this experimental model [98], which is associated with the activation of Na^+, K^+ -ATPase in the renal cortex and a decrease in gentamicin accumulation in the kidneys. And in this case the higher dose of the extract of 1 g/kg providing the sufficient quantity of potassium was the most effective, still both doses (100 mg/kg and 1 g/kg) contributed to normokalemia maintenance, in contrast to the untreated control group. But on the other hand, it is of great importance for a nephrotropic agent not to cause hyperkalemia, and this was confirmed on the severe models of acute kidney injury. Thus, hyperkalemia was not registered against the background of the extract on the models of ischemic acute renal failure and even glycerol-induced myoglobinuric acute renal failure, since the possibilities to excrete excessive potassium were maintained [39]. In the further studies on the models without primary kidney injury, negative effects that could be linked to hyperkalemia were not registered either (the exception was the model with the administration of high doses of allopurinol against the background of excessive purine derivatives and proteins intake, under such conditions intratubular obstruction by xanthine concretions is possible in rodents, thus excluding the use of the agents with the high content of potassium) [99].

At the same time, ambiguous results were obtained after verification of goutweed extract efficacy under the conditions of the prolonged (10 weeks) administration of HCTZ (20 mg/kg) with excess fructose (the efficacy of potassium supplementation as well as blood uric acid decrease were confirmed as pathogenetically important on this model [100] thus substantiating the study of goutweed preparations possessing the mentioned types of pharmacological activity). Exceptionally in this model, the single per day administration of goutweed extract as source of potassium salts led to adverse changes associated with increased aldosterone control (other factors contributing to the latter were hydrochlorothiazide and low-sodium diet). It should be noted that such combination of factors is hardly achievable in practice [99, 101].

Thus, time factor and specificity of dose regimen are crucial for the influence on aldosterone control (potassium chloride quick administration would obviously led to the similar shifts in renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system). At the same time, other positive effects of the extract were realized, namely the hypouricemic effect was evident even under these aggravated conditions, and when acute hyperuricemia was additionally reproduced on this model by uricase inhibition, the extract contributed to kidney function maintenance and decreased protein excretion [99, 101].

At the same time, the favourable interrelationship between the influence on glucose metabolism and potassium exchange was seen in the effect of goutweed tincture against the background of high doses of dexamethasone causing insulin resistance [99]. This agent itself did not cause shifts in the functional state of the kidneys, including the signs of mineralocorticoid control enhancement, while there was an increase in potassium plasma level. This change can be associated with the redistribution of the cation between the tissue pool and the blood plasma, which is closely interconnected with the effects of insulin (its ability to increase the flow of K^+ into

cells is well known). A moderate increase in kalemia was registered in diabetic patients treated with metformin, and when glibenclamide was added, this increase was not evident against the background of increased normoglycemic effect of the combined therapy [102]. In our study, combined treatment of the rats receiving high doses of dexamethasone with subtherapeutic dose of metformine combined with goutweed tincture allowed normalizing both of kalemia and insulin sensitivity (which was not achieved by monotherapy with metformin at the dose used) [99].

The entirety of the data obtained in our phytopharmacological study, allowed to give comparative characteristic of goutweed preparations depending on extractant type and dosage. Potassium content as well as the level of other active substances, is also among the factors determining these preparations activity. Goutweed tincture after extractant removal is much more effective on the models of carbohydrate metabolism disorders than goutweed extract that may be caused by optimal content of hydroxycinnamic acids in the tincture, lower intake of flavonoids compared with the extract, the differences in the relative content of these substances, as well as lower content of potassium compounds. At the same time, goutweed extract possessing the favourable combination of potassium compounds high content with nephroprotective, hypoazotemic, hypouricemic and uricosuric activity is promising for counteraction to kidney diseases pathogenesis as well as to uric acid metabolism disorders (the tincture is also effective in the latter case) [39, 40, 99].

7. Modulation of the effects of hydrochlorothiazide by herbal agents

The problem of interaction of herbal agents with widely used drugs remains relevant. In the context of counteraction to the side effects of thiazide diuretics, hypouricemic effect inherent in numerous preparations of herbal origin [7] could be beneficial, as well as their ability to supplement potassium that was discussed above. At the

same time, the verified data on medicinal plants interaction with diuretics are not abundant at all. For instance, the extract of extract *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. (*Malvaceae*) enhanced diuretic response to hydrochlorothiazide, increased its concentration in plasma and prolonged its excretion [103]. Homogenate of garlic *Allium sativum* L. (*Aliaceae*) and water extract of tea *Thea sinensis* L. (*Theaceae*) exerted synergistic cardioprotective properties with hydrochlorothiazide in rats with myocardial damage induced by isoproterenol [104, 105], though these studies had not addressed renal function and water-salt metabolism changes.

The herbal drugs may provide benefits due to the complex composition, in which high potassium content is supplemented with the substances exerting beneficial metabolic effects, e.g. hydroxycinnamic acids and flavonoids. Such features are inherent in the object of our studies, goutweed (*Aegopodium podagraria* L.) aerial part extract. In the absence of additional aggravating factors intensifying aldosterone control (described in the previous section), the extract effectively counteracted to the side effects of hydrochlorothiazide. Thus, administration of hydrochlorothiazide at a dose causing metabolic disorders (80 mg/kg for 16 days) in combination with goutweed extract (100 mg/kg and 1 g/kg) allowed maintaining normokalemia and an adequate potassium excretion, the influence on sodium excretion depended on dose and regimen of kidney function. After a single administration, GW extract dose-dependently changed the natriuretic effect of hydrochlorothiazide (20 mg/kg), which was maintained against the background of the extract at a dose of 1 g/kg (as well as the reference drug potassium chloride at a dose which is potassium cation equivalent corresponding to this dose of the extract), but not at a dose of 100 mg/kg, while its diuretic effect was eliminated [99, 106].

Course administration of hydrochlorothiazide (80 g/kg for 3 weeks) did not result in any changes indicating severe tox-

icity in rats, while plasma potassium content was reduced, the indirect evidence of intravascular fluid volume decrease was seen (which was eliminated by the extract at higher dose), and the tolerance to some of the renal effects developed. Potassium excretion was maximal in the group receiving goutweed extract at a higher dose in all experiments, but in all groups of the treated animals, kalemia did not differ significantly from the intact control value. The extract supported natriuresis in water loading test due to the decrease in the distal transport of sodium, which was also observed in rats treated with potassium chloride, and did not influence on it under the conditions of spontaneous diuresis. It is important that the renal effects of the extract linked to potassium supplementation were favourably combined with its uricosuric action (at higher dose) and hypoazotemic activity (plasma urea level decreased under the influence of both doses) [99, 106].

In general, the results of our studies indicate that goutweed preparations pharmacodynamics is characterized by the combination of hypoglycemic, nephroprotective, hepatoprotective, antiinflammatory properties as well as ability to normalize uric acid metabolism. The specifics of action of each preparation was also described as mentioned above. In the context of the present work, such prospects (substantiated by the discussed data) could be emphasized as the use of the extract as nephroprotector and the use of both preparations in uric acid metabolism disorders.

9. General conclusions

Undoubtedly, the solving the health problems arising with the development of urbanized civilization (and we express high hopes that this development nevertheless will be continued) is in all probability possible only through the use of high technologies. On this way it is expedient to rethink the commonly used ideas about an unspecific and uncertain mode of action of phytotherapy and to use the heritage of traditional medicine, the experience of food

plants usage for the development of the standardized herbal drugs with proven activity [99]. There is a need of integration and use of the previously obtained evidence (including non-English journals), which often contain valuable data, including those obtained *in vivo*, still is often inaccessible to the majority of researches.

For the future development of the renal phytopharmacology, it is crucial to integrate fundamental approaches to the excretory renal function evaluation (correct estimation and analysis at the different regimens of kidney functioning) with the most modern methodological level of phytochemical and biochemical studies.

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АНАЛІЗ ПИТАННЯ ЩОДО ДІАГНОСТИКИ, ЛІКУВАННЯ ТА СУДОВО-МЕДИЧНОЇ ЕКСПЕРТИЗИ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗКОВОЇ ТРАВМИ: СТАН ТА ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ ВДОСКОНАЛЕННЯ (ОГЛЯД)

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АНАЛИЗ ВОПРОСА ДИАГНОСТИКИ, ЛЕЧЕНИЯ И СУДЕБНО-МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ЭКСПЕРТИЗЫ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗГОВОЙ ТРАВМЫ: СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ (ОБЗОР)

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ANALYSIS OF THE ISSUE REGARDING THE DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION OF TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY: STATUS AND PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVEMENT (REVIEW)

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Summary/Резюме

The review article presents data on the prevalence and mortality of traumatic brain injury (TBI). An analysis of modern principles of diagnosis and treatment of patients with TBI is presented, including against the background of concomitant pathology, especially in the presence of acute blood loss (on the basis of standards, protocols and guidelines). The main problems arising in the diagnosis and treatment of TBI, therapeutic and diagnostic defects are given. The main aspects of forensic medical examination of TBI abroad and in Ukraine, as well as problematic issues and defects of forensic medical expert assessment of TBI are highlighted. Prospective directions for solving existing problems in diagnosis, treatment and forensic assessment of TBI are indicated.

Key words: *forensic medical examination, brain brain injury, defect, acute blood loss.*